

CHAPTER 6: THE ORIGINS OF DIRECT MARITIME TRADE WITH THE FAR EAST

Having observed the increasing Sasanian activity in maritime trade with India, the question remains as to whether or not there was direct maritime contact between the Gulf and the Far East in Sasanian and very early Islamic times, as there undoubtedly was by the 8th century. As we shall see, the wealth of the ^CAbbāsīd entrepôts was based on the Islamic monopoly, or near monopoly of the carrying trade to China and the Far East. We must ask whether Rīshahr was a predecessor to Sīrāf in this respect.

First, it is necessary to examine the evidence for competition in the carrying trade and in the Gulf itself from Chinese vessels, and then to discuss the evidence for the activity of Gulf Arabs or Persians in the Far East. Our sources are extremely diverse and often somewhat confused. As a result, both questions have been the subject of considerable dispute among scholars. For this reason, and since the origins of direct sailing have considerable bearing on the later history of the Gulf, the problem will be discussed at some length.

Scholarship has been sharply divided over the question of Chinese activity in the Gulf in the Sasanian period. The majority of scholars have lent credence to passages in Tabarī, Mas^Cūdī, and the Liu Sung shu, among others, which imply that Chinese ships were a common sight in the Gulf in the latter part of the Sasanian

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period. Far Eastern scholars such as Ferrand and Pelliot,¹ Roman historians such as Warmington,² and Islamic scholars such as Reinault, Caetani, and Sauvaget have accepted this view.³ Sauvaget, for example in the introduction to his magisterial edition of the Akhbār as-Sīn wa'l-Hind wrote that "de leur côté les Chinois poussaient jusqu'en plein Golfe Persique" and went as far as to suggest that "il faudra même admettre que les Chinois ont contribué à initier les Arabes à la navigation vers l'Extrême-Orient." Yule, Hudson, and most recently Needham all with varying reservations have accepted the probability of Chinese navigation in the Gulf before the Hejira.⁴

The contrary view has been forcibly stated by other scholars. Hirth and Rockhill, for example, after a detailed examination of evidence felt able to assert categorically that Quilon in southwest India was the furthest point west ever reached by Chinese ships till the Ming dynasty.⁵ More recently Hourani in an article specifically devoted to the question concluded that "there is nothing to prove direct Chinese sailings to Mesopotamia before Islam. Nor, I believe do we find them for many centuries after Islam."⁶

Unfortunately, none of these writers seem to have had the full range of information on hand, and there is a great deal of confusion about individual sources. So an attempt will be made first, to review these sources, starting with the Islamic and the Roman sources, then proceeding to the Chinese, before assessing the picture they present.

The sources which have been most often used to prove Chinese maritime activity in the Gulf in the Sasanian period are the early Islamic historians. Thus, Ṭabarī, Balādhurī, and Dīnawarī, each apparently following the same tradition, write that at the time of the Muslim conquest Ubullah was frequented by ships from China (sufūn min al-Sīn), India, Oman, and Bahrain.⁷

Mas'ūdī records that ships of China (sufūn al-Sīn) and of India used to sail to Hira in Sasanian times. In its details his story is unreliable, for ocean going ships certainly never have reached Hira and additionally, the account was attributed to a 360 year old Nestorian (!) who recounted the tale to Khālid ibn al-Walīd in 630.⁸ However, in its general form the reference is strikingly similar to those of the earlier historians. Elsewhere Mas'ūdī adds fresh material which is of particular value since he had personally visited the sea ports of the Gulf and had sailed on the Indian Ocean. He writes of Ḡalah in Malaya that it was the meeting place of ships from China and the Gulf, but that it had not always been so. For "the ships of China [marākib al-Sīn] used to sail to Oman, Sīrāf, the coast of Fārs, Bahrain, Ubullah, and Baṣra, while the ships of these countries used to sail direct to China."⁹ This last passage might refer to former Sasanian trade, but it is also possible that Mas'ūdī (writing c. 947) describes the disruption of trade after the sack of Canton in 878, following which the Arab fleets used to sail no further east than Ḡalah in Malaya.¹⁰ Regardless of the exact

date to which Mas^cūdī refers, it seems that he considered Chinese junks had sailed in the Gulf before the 10th century. In view of the other historical references it would appear quite likely that this was during the Sasanian period.¹¹

However, before passing on to other sources, it is necessary to examine the exact meanings of the original Arabic. Thus sufūn min al-Sīn, as used by Ṭabari, Balādhuri, and Dīnawari, means ships coming from China and does not necessarily imply that these ships were Chinese. Furthermore, Hirth and Hourani have suggested that sufūn al-Sīn or marākib al-Sīn may refer to Muslim ships on the China run with the same significance as "East India men" or "China Clippers" in English. Hourani suggested that this represented the sense in which markab Sīni was used in the 9th and 10th century sources. However, to support his contention he produced evidence of actual usage from only one source. This is a passage in the ʿAjaib, the great 10th-11th century collection of travellers' tales which refers to a markab Sīni captained by a notable Persian sailor ʿAbhara.¹² The very same passage was used by Sauvaget, who interpreted it in a directly contrary sense as evidence that the Chinese introduced Gulf merchants to the navigation of the Southern Seas.¹³ This difficult section is given in full:

Among the yarns of seamen and shipmasters is that which is told about Captain ʿAbharah. He was originally from Kimān, a shepherd in one of its districts, then he became a fisherman, then one of the sailors on a ship trading with

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India. He then changed to a China ship [markab Sīni] of which he afterwards became captain. He was well-versed in the ways of the sea and made the voyage to China seven times. No one had crossed to China before him except as a perilous adventure.¹⁴

To evaluate this passage it is necessary to note that at least one source refers to China boats using a less ambiguous expression than does the ^cAjaib. This is the Akhbār as-Sīn wa'l-Hind, a collection of travel stories and miscellaneous accounts of India and China which was compiled in the middle of the 9th century. It deserves particular attention because it was composed on the Gulf itself and reflects stories circulating among the merchants.¹⁵ Twice the author refers to Chinese ships as al-sufūn al-Sīniyah, which is a considerably stronger use of the possessive than the phrase markab Sīni in the ^cAjaib. Thus Needham, while accepting that sufūn al-Sīn or marākib al-Sīn may refer to Gulf sailors on the China run, considers that sufūn al-Sīniyah must refer to native Chinese boats.¹⁶

The references to al-sufūn al-Sīniyah occur in the itinerary from Sīrāf to China (paras. 13-16) immediately following the famous section on the Muslim colony in Canton as reported by the merchant Sulayman.¹⁷ The Chinese ships (al-sufūn al-Sīniyah) loaded at Sīrāf and sailed past Masqat to Kulam Malay on the Malabar coast where shipping was taxed at a military post. The author writes "from the Chinese 1,000 dirhams is levied, and from the

remaining ships 10-[20] dinars".¹⁸ From Kulam Malay the boats sailed onwards to Canton. The Akhbār does not give a specific source for the itinerary but implies regular sailing. If we are to accept the normal interpretation of al-sufūn al-Sīniyah, this then is positive evidence that junks regularly sailed from the Gulf to Canton during the 9th century or possibly earlier, and suggests that ambiguous passages in other writers referring to the Sasanian period may also refer to junks.

However, the problem is not so much the grammatical meaning of the Arabic, but the understanding of it by our sources. These appear to fall into three groups. The first are the historians who speak of sufūn min al-Sīn. The second are the sources based on oral tradition current in the Gulf in the 9th and 10th centuries. These include the Akhbār and the Ajaib, both of which are written in a colloquial rather than literary style. Mas'ūdī too most probably either based his accounts on oral evidence he had heard in the Gulf and had perhaps misunderstood, or on a manuscript of the Akhbār on which he drew so freely that Quatremère has proposed to consider that he wrote it.¹⁹ The third group of sources are probably derivative. These include Ibn al-Faḥīḥ²⁰ and undoubtedly others.

The evidence from the first group with which we are primarily concerned could well refer to Sasanian shipping, which we see below

almost certainly reached Chinese waters. The third group can be disregarded. The second group of sources, though they need not refer to any period earlier than the eighth century are the best evidence for Chinese shipping at that period and, by inference, at the earlier period. I am in no position to evaluate their style, but Sauvaget, who was, notes that it is extremely rough and colloquial,²¹ so there does seem to be a greater intrinsic possibility that these broke the normal rules of grammar by calling Muslim shipping sufūn al-Sīn, than did the other sources.

There are great difficulties in accepting this second group of references about Chinese ships. The trading cities of the Gulf are well recorded in the 9th and 10th centuries by local writers such as the authors of the Akhbār, the Ajaib, and Abū Zayd, and by men who had direct contact with Gulf merchants such as Iṣṭakhri and Ibn Ḥawqal.²² However, despite the wealth of local colour which they give, there are no references to Chinese in these ports, which is particularly puzzling since one would assume they would have had a certain curiosity value, at least to outsiders like Iṣṭakhri or Ibn Ḥawqal. It is equally surprising that the Akhbār, in its long discussion of Chinese customs, clothes, and habits, does not indicate that any visited Sīrāf. We hear of Chinese products, Chinese ships, and even Chinese coins circulating at Sīrāf,²³ without a single reference to Chinamen.

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In addition there seem to be no clear references to Chinese elsewhere in the Indian Ocean at this period. A passage from Idrīsī on the Rālej or Zānej Islands has been advanced as evidence of Chinese factories off the East African coast in the 10th century,²⁴ and an enormous Chinese population there has been suggested by more adventurous writers.²⁵ However, Idrīsī's description of Africa is full of difficult passages. For example, it is concluded in Chapter 12 that he conflated Sofāla in Gujerat with its namesake on the African coast. His passage on the Rālej or Zānej Islands²⁶ is particularly difficult because of its similarity in Arabic with Zabāj (Indonesia) which would far better fit the description of the islands which he claimed, for example grew camphor. As a result, many scholars have concluded that Idrīsī's Zānej Islands are a confused account of Śrīvijaya, which always had close contacts with China, and that he reflects the well known Indonesian activity off the African coast rather than that of the Chinese.²⁷ The Indonesian explanation of this passage appears much the more probable.

Thus we can summarize the Islamic evidence. It contains no specific reference to Chinese maritime traders that I am aware of till after the 10th century. The sole references are to Chinese goods and Chinese ships. It is almost impossible that the latter could be junks piloted by Arabs, for our information on shipping clearly refers to boats of Islamic types.²⁸ Despite this,

the evidence for Chinese shipping in significant quantities in the western Indian Ocean and the Gulf during Sasanian times and the first few centuries of Islam is strong and fairly specific. The contrary evidence is not sufficient, from Islamic sources alone, to dismiss the possibility that the Chinese played a significant role in the development of Gulf commerce during this period.

By itself then the Islamic evidence is inconclusive, and it is necessary to see whether evidence from other sources clarifies the picture. A single Roman source is relevant. Warmington concluded from a passage in Ammianus Marcellinus that both Indian and Chinese ships frequented the Fair at Batnae on the Euphrates.²⁹ However, the text does not warrant such a conclusion since it merely states that Indian and Chinese goods were sold at Batnae (convenit multitudo, ad commercanda quae Indi mittunt et Seres). Moreover, the name for China employed here, Seres, is generally taken to mean inland China, as approached by the overland route, rather than maritime China as reached by sea.³⁰

The earliest Chinese reference which has a bearing on the problem occurs in Chapter 97 of the Annals of the Liu-Sung Dynasty,* written about 500 A.D. and referring to the period 420-478.³¹ It is an important passage which has received a great deal of scholarly

* The transliteration of Chinese characters is as far as possible that adopted by Wolters, p. 7 (modified from Wade's Syllabary). Elsewhere transliterations are from Wolters or, lacking these, as found.

attention, and as a result four complete or partial translations were available to me. The varying interpretations of the text, besides their value for the study of this passage, provide a classic example of the problems confronting a non-Sinologist who ventures to discuss Chinese material.

The first translation was that of F. Hirth:

As regards the Ta-ts'in³² [The eastern Mediterranean] and T'ien-chu [northern India] we have to say that although the envoys of the two Han dynasties have experienced the special difficulties of this route, yet trade has been carried on, and goods have been sent out to the foreign tribes, the force of the wind driving them far across the waves of the sea. . . . All the precious things of land and water come from there. . . . all this has caused navigation and trade to be extended to these parts.³³ [My italics]

On the surface this seems a crucial passage, clearly implying that Chinese exports were being sent directly to the West by sea as early as the 5th century.

However, though recent research has suggested no modification of the Chinese characters of the text, it has indicated some very significant alterations to the translation. The central italicized section is rendered by Wang Gungwu as follows, "But still the supply of merchandise has been kept up being sent out from the Chiau area [Tonking] across the waves."³⁴ Wolters however, after consulting both earlier translations believed he was justified in reading it in a contrary sense, as referring to Chinese imports rather than to exports. He reads the italicized portion: "and the merchandise on

which [China] depended had come from Tonking. It had sailed on the waves of the sea, and travelling from afar to [China]".³⁵

The final section of the passage, which is rendered by Hirth as "all this has caused trade and navigation to be extended to these parts" was translated in a significantly different manner by Wang Gungwu and J. Needham, both of whom imply the existence of trading intermediaries. Wang Gungwu translates "thus there is a chain of great and small ships on the route and the merchants and (trading) envoys (gather to) exchange. . . ." ³⁶ Needham suggests that "the chou (perhaps Chinese ships) and the po (perhaps foreign ships)'make connection along the route.' " ³⁷ Wolters translates this portion as "ships came in a continuous stream and merchants and envoys jostled with each other", and considers that this is "the clearest evidence that the merchandise was brought to China by foreigners rather than fetched by Chinese." ³⁸ Certainly it is not so clear to me. It seems only possible to conclude that the passage is so obscure that it cannot be used as evidence of Chinese activity in the western Indian Ocean.

A later reference is in an article of Pelliot's of 1929, in which he drew our attention to Ta-Houan, a Chinese captured at the battle of Talas in 751. Ta-Houan's own account of his travels is lost, but fragments are preserved in the work of a contemporary. ³⁹ From these it is clear that Ta-Houan returned from Mesopotamia to China by sea. Pelliot paraphrases this section of the text as

follows: "une Jonque marchande l'avait ramené du Golfe Persique a Canton."⁴⁰ This statement appears without amplification and could merely indicate that Ta-Houan returned by sea, for Tibbetts mentions that the terms from which we have derived "junk" were originally used for any large ocean going boat, irrespective of its country of origin.⁴¹

From a slightly later date there is an itinerary of the route from Canton to the lands of the Arabs which was composed by Kia Tan between 785 and 805,⁴² but which may refer to an earlier period. Even if it is based on contemporary accounts, it predates by over fifty years first Arab itinerary for the Gulf or the Indian Ocean.⁴³ The route from China to the west coast of India is relatively straightforward, and has been studied in detail by Pelliot.⁴⁴ However, the ports of call from the Indus onwards have posed considerable problems of identification. Hirth and Rockhill, who first published the text, identified them as follows:

Ti-lo-lu-ho or Lo-ho-i, twenty days journey west of the Indus, with a light house-Cape Musandam.

Wu-la, one day westward-Suhār.

Mo-lo, an important market of the Ta-shi, two days journey up the Fu-li-la River-Hurmuz.

From there to the capital of the Prince of the Faithful, called Fu-ta, was 1000 li (about 500 km.). The route doubled back on itself rather seriously (from Cape Musandam to Suhār, and then back to Hurmuz), while it is hard to locate a major capital 500 km.

from Hurmuz. The editors concluded that the Chinese had no knowledge at all of the route beyond the west coast of India and that Kia Tan had been deliberately misled by Muslim informants who wished to conceal the secrets of navigation in the Western Ocean.⁴⁵

However, the irregularity of the itinerary is only a problem if one accepts Hirth and Rockhill's identifications. More convincing identifications are provided by Lewicki: that Ti-lo-lu-ho is Qishm Island (Jazīrat al-Tiwāl), which according to Ibn Khurdādhbih was about twenty days journey from the Indus; that Wu-la is Ubullah on the river Ti-lo (Digla-Tigris), which is situated two days from Qishm Island on Ibn Khurdādhbih's itinerary, and about 500 kilometres (1,000 li) from Baghdad, the seat of the Prince of the Faithful, and Ctesiphon, the Sasanian capital.⁴⁶ The itinerary thus presented corresponds with Ibn Khurdādhbih's coasting itinerary. By the 9th century it is clear that this itinerary was becoming obsolete, for both Ibn Khurdādhbih and Sulaymān provide itineraries sailing direct with the monsoon from the Gulf to South India.⁴⁷ Could it be then that Kia Tan was recording an earlier voyage before monsoon sailing became so common? Just as possibly he simply records the voyage of boats which continued to use the coasting itinerary. Whatever his source, it seems to have been outstandingly accurate, and there seems no reason to believe that he was deliberately misled.

These three passages, the ambiguous Liu Sung Shu reference, the piece published by Pelliot, and Kia Tan's itinerary, appear to be the total extent of direct references in the Chinese sources which could apply to Chinese shipping in the western Indian Ocean during this period. However, before considering other Chinese evidence, the archaeological material must be summarized.

One possible archaeological trace of Chinese maritime activity close to the borders of the Sasanian Empire comes from the Ajanta Caves, a group of Buddhist cave sanctuaries 400 kilometres north-east of Bombay. Among the paintings in Cave 2,⁴⁸ executed in the first half of the 6th century (though frequently misdated to the 7th century),⁴⁹ is one of a three masted boat with high taut sails, reminiscent of the Chinese matt and batton type. Thus Schoff in 1905 concluded that "if not a junk [it was] manifestly influenced by that type of vessel!"⁵⁰ Other scholars in the field of maritime history, such as Donnelly and possibly Hornell considered the ship was Chinese.⁵¹ The Indian scholar Mookerji determined that it was Indian,⁵² and the Persian Hādī Hasan not only decided that it was Persian, but that it was the ship which carried Persian envoys to the court of the Pulakesin Raja of the Deccan in 628!⁵³ More recently Bowen, while recognizing that "the ship has tall Chinese lug sails", notes that:

the hull of the vessel indicated that it is undoubtedly indigenous; there is certainly no resemblance to the junk hull. The hull bears strong resemblance to the ships shown on the second century A.D. (Coromandel) coins and to the

recently extant Sinhalese coaster. The projection of the beam ends through the skin of the planks is not of typical Chinese design but rather has affinities with Egypt, India, Burma, and Indonesia.

Further, he considered that even high lugged sails, although influenced by Chinese designs, represented an indigenous Indian type which has since disappeared.⁵⁴ Needham, after noting parallels with Roman, Sinhalese, Egyptian, and Chinese boats, concluded the probability that "the artist was unthinkingly combining characteristics from a number of different sea-going vessels which he had seen but not looked at, and it is not surprising to find certain Chinese elements among them".⁵⁵ With such a confused position, the Ajanta ship can hardly be taken as definitive evidence for junks putting in at the predecessor of Bombay. Besides, if there are Chinese elements, these could have been picked up from observation of junks as far away as Bengal or Ceylon.

The evidence of archaeological finds elsewhere is essentially negative. Chinese coins from the 7th century onwards are recorded both from the Gulf (at Sīrāf) and from Zanzibar. These early finds, however, occur in hoards which include other Chinese coins as late as the 13th century A.D., and may have found their way there at any time before that period.⁵⁶ Although Chinese pottery is very common on the Gulf (and rarer elsewhere) from the 9th century onwards, no finds at all are known from Sasanian levels.⁵⁷

If the evidence for Chinese activity in the Gulf seems slight, this is not because the Chinese were uninterested in the seaways. With the break up of the Han and the barbarian invasions, culminating in those of the T'o-pa Wei (4th century) there was a considerable shift in population away from the traditional centres of Chinese culture on the Yellow River towards the less developed Yangtze basin. Except for a brief period under the Chin, China was divided between two, or sometimes three, rival dynasties. Those centred on the Yangtze, which became increasingly prosperous, were, except for short periods, effectively barred access to the land routes to the West, and as a result, looked increasingly toward the sea. This process, which will be described in greater detail in the second part of this chapter, is of the greatest importance for the development of Asian maritime trade, and, as will be seen, had repercussions of considerable importance as far away as the Persian Gulf. Indeed, it is in the context of the migration of the Chin Dynasty south that the passage in the Liu Sung Shu appears which was discussed above.⁵⁸

Thus, in the third century a Chinese mission was sent under K'ang T'ai to Tun-sun (Malaya) and obtained there information on the sea route to the West.⁵⁹ Already Chinese merchants were trading to India, for a lost work of K'ang T'ai records a certain Chia Hsiang-Li who had traded to India and back.⁶⁰ By the end of

the 4th century Chinese were crossing the ocean to Ceylon.⁶¹ The tempo of maritime trade increased all over Southern Asia, yet, although China was the greatest market in the area, there is little evidence that Chinese shipping played an important part in this trade.

Fa-Hsien, for example, who visited Ceylon in the 5th century and was made homesick merely by seeing a Chinese fan there would certainly have mentioned it if there had been other Chinese, or even many Chinese objects in Ceylon.⁶² None of the numerous Chinese pilgrims of the 7th century whose voyages to South East Asia and Ceylon are recorded by I-Ching travelled on Chinese boats.⁶³ A 6th century source refers to foreign shipping at Canton,⁶⁴ while Chinese merchants who sought foreign goods seem to have had dealings with K'un-lun (Indonesian) rather than with Chinese shipping.⁶⁵ An eighth century source presents a similar picture. "The sea going junks are foreign ships. Every year they come to Canton and An-i. Those from Ceylon are the largest!"⁶⁶ Even the names of Sīrāf or Aden are not mentioned by Chinese sources prior to the late 12th century.⁶⁷

Thus, as will be seen in the second half of the Chapter, Chinese shipping played a secondary role in long distance commerce, even east of Ceylon. Given this large amount of negative Chinese evidence and the doubts that have been cast on the Islamic data,

it seems impossible to support the thesis that Chinese shipping was common in the Gulf in the Sasanian and early Islamic periods, or that the Chinese played a significant role in the development of long distance Gulf commerce. Nevertheless, the essentially negative Chinese evidence does not quite explain the almost certain references in the Islamic sources to Chinese ships.

There is a possibility that the so-called "Chinese ships" were not Chinese at all, but actually Malayan or Indonesian. For we know from K'ang T'ai that already in the third century Malayan princes were obtaining horses from the Indo-Scythians of the Indus, and from there it would be little extra journey to the Persian Gulf.⁶⁸ Indonesian seafarers were active in the eastern Indian Ocean, and it is possible that despite the racial differentiation, they could have been confused with Chinese when they reached the Gulf. This is one way the evidence of the Chinese texts could be explained.

It is probably not necessary, however, to look for a confusion between Malays and Chinese as an explanation of the references to China ships. For there is evidence which might be relevant to this study in the accounts of the exchange of embassies between Iran and China.

Mas^c ūdī and Ya^c qūbī, probably using a common source, describe one such embassy in the section of their brief histories of China

on King Haratan. The Chinese ruler:

had ships made on which men were embarked to take the most precious products of China to Sind, India, the areas of Babylonia, and all lands near and far from the sea coast. They were to offer the rulers of these countries marvellous and valuable presents and to bring back their finest products . . . information on their government, religions, laws and customs, as well as giving strangers the taste for precious stones, perfumes and manufactured goods from China. The ships dispersed in all directions, travelled to foreign lands and executed their orders. . . .

As a result, "the princes of the maritime states had ships made also, in which they sent those products of their lands which were strange, began to have relations with the Ruler of China, and sent him gifts in return."⁶⁹

The account of Haratan, and indeed the whole section on Chinese history in Ya^cqūbī and Mas^cūdī appears to have no direct parallel in the Chinese records, but it cannot be a complete fabrication. For the passage excerpted agrees to an almost uncanny extent with Chinese concepts of "semi-diplomatic semi-mercantile missions".⁷⁰ In almost every respect the motifs of Haratan's mission agree with the account of the Li-Tai Thung Chien Chi Lan (18th century) regarding the reasons for Cheng-Ho's famous voyages in the 15th century.⁷¹ It is particularly striking that these Islamic sources seem to have grasped that concept of commerce which the Chinese seem so often to have favoured. This is a concept not of trade which implies a certain degree of equality between the trading partners, but one of gifts from the Son of Heaven which were returned in the form of tribute from his inferiors, the foreign barbarians.

Thus it seems almost inconceivable that the Islamic account was not based on some Chinese oral or written source. Could it have been then, that the Chinese ships which old men remembered seeing at Ubullah were not simply rare and adventurous merchants, but actually Chinese embassies?

Only one Chinese mission during the Sasanian period seems to be specifically mentioned in the Islamic texts. Mas'ūdī records an envoy from the King of China to Khusrau I (531-579) with the gift of a horse and rider made of precious stones and clothed in silk. Unfortunately there is no information as to whether the mission travelled by land or sea.⁷²

The Chinese sources, as one would expect, are more helpful. The first embassy from China to Parthia in 97 B.C. came overland.⁷³ Later embassies from Parthia were sent in 87 and 101 A.D.,⁷⁴ but we cannot tell whether they went by land or sea. Persian envoys (the identification of posse=Persian will be discussed at length below) do not reappear in the Chinese annals till 455,⁷⁵ when they travelled to the court of the northern, inland dynasty, the Wei. Presumably these envoys too came by land. Persian envoys to the south Chinese dynasties first appear in 530, 533, and 535, a period which coincides with the date of the break up of the northern Wei, who for more than a century had closed the overland route through Central Asia to the South Chinese. It seems then that these were

probably the same overland missions which had previously gone to the northern Wei, and were temporarily diverted south while the Wei princes and generals struggled for power.⁷⁶

The Chinese are more silent about any Chinese missions which might have preceded or followed the Persian embassies.⁷⁷ After the mission of Kan Ying in 97 A.D.,⁷⁸ there seems to be no mention of an embassy to Persia until the Sui period when one was sent between 605 and 617.⁷⁹ There is no information about whether or not this embassy came by sea. Certainly at this period the land routes were exceptionally busy and, as we shall see below, the Chinese were making every effort to encourage the overland trade.⁸⁰ This same period, however, did see the first seaborne mission to Malaya and the Southern Seas.⁸¹ since that of K'ang T'ai and Chu-Ying in the third century.⁸² Could it be that some such mission proceeded to the Persian Gulf under the Sui or that a maritime mission was sent by the Liang to Khusrau I (531-579), when their brief period of access to the land route (530-535) had ended. The memory of such a voyage or series of voyages could well have lingered among the Arabs and been later recorded, just as the memory of Cheng-Ho survived at Calicut 800 years later.⁸³

NOTES

¹G. Ferrand, "Les relations de la Chine avec le Golfe Persique avant l'Hégire", Mélanges Gaudefroy-Demombynes, Cairo 1935-1945, pp. 131-140; P. Pelliot, "Des artisans chinois à la capitale Abbasside en 751-762", T'oung Pao XXVI, 1929, p. 110.

²E. H. Warmington, The Commerce Between the Roman Empire and India, Cambridge 1928, pp. 138, 358 note 146.

³J. T. Reinaud, Relations des voyages faits par les Arabes et les Persans dans l'Inde dans le IXe siècle de l'ère chrétienne, Paris 1845, I, p. XXXV; L. Caetani, Annali dell'Islam, Milan 1905-26, II(2), sect. 133, note 1, III, sect. 328; J. Sauvaget in "Introduction" to Akhbār, p. xxxix; Heyd I, p. 7; Tibbetts, Pre-Islamic Arabia, p. 207.

⁴Yule, Cathay, I, p. 84; Hudson, p. 113; Needham, I, especially p. 179.

⁵F. Hirth and W. W. Rockhill in CJK, Introduction, especially p. 18. J. J. L. Duyvendak, China's Discovery of Africa, London 1949, p. 16 comes to the same conclusion.

⁶Hourani, especially pp. 46-50; G. Hourani, "Direct Sailing Between the Persian Gulf and China in Pre-Islamic Times", J.R.A.S., 1947, pp. 157-160.

⁷Ṭabarī I, p. 2383; Balādhurī, p. 341; Dīnawarī, ed. Kratchovskiy, p. 123. The major Islamic sources are discussed at length in Chapter 2 above.

⁸Mas'ūdī, Murūj, I, pp. 216, 219, trans. I, p. 88. Hourani, p. 47, considered that the whole episode was legendary because of the fabulous age of Khalid's informant (p. 219) and the impossibility in the historical past of navigation by ocean going ships to Hira. However these legendary embellishments need not necessarily invalidate a genuine historical reminiscence of Chinese junks.

⁹Mas'ūdī, Murūj I, p. 308, trans. I, p. 127.

¹⁰This is the suggestion of Hourani, pp. 77-78. Qalah is on the Malay peninsula and its location is discussed at length in Wheatly, pp. 216-224. Abū Zayd, p. 61, (10th century) describes it as the terminus for the ships from Sirāf; cf. 9th century sources, Ibn Kh., p. 62 and Akhbār, sect. 15.

¹¹Sir H. Yule (Cathay and the Way Thither, 1st edition, London 1866, I) suggested that a passage in Hamza noted the presence of Chinese boats at Hira in the 5th century and on Yule's authority this has been accepted by such scholars as Hornell, Mookerji, and most recently Tibbetts, despite the contrary note by Cordonier (Yule, Cathay, I, p. 83). The passage in Hamza, p. 102, parallels Mas'udi's in Mas'udi, Muruj I, p. 216 to the extent that it notes that Hira had formerly been by the sea, but there is no mention of Chinese, or any other shipping at its wharves.

¹²Hourani, p. 47; ^cAjaib, sect 46; Introduction to CJK p.15 n. 3.

¹³Sauvaget in Akhbār, p. xxxix.

^{14c}Ajaib, sect. 46, trans. Hourani, p. 114.

¹⁵The Akhbār is discussed in greater detail in Chapter 7.

¹⁶Needham I, p. 179, note k. Needham I, p. 16 acknowledges assistance on Arabic-Chinese cultural contacts from D. M. Dunlop.

¹⁷Sulaymān's report in section 12.

¹⁸For the location of Kulam Malay see notes by Sauvaget to Akhbār, pp. 42-43 and Tibbetts, p. 458 who identify it with Quilon. [20] dinars in the text is an addition by Sauvaget from the text of Ibn al-Faqīh, p. 12. The large size of boats sailing to China is noted in the second part of this Chapter.

¹⁹The literary style and contribution of the Akhbār to other works are discussed by Sauvaget in the Introduction to Akhbār. Quatremère seems to have been the only scholar to attribute the Akhbār to Mas'udi.

²⁰e.g. Ibn al-Faqīh, p. 11. Sauvaget, Introduction to Akhbār discusses his debt to the Akhbār, p. xxiv. Further research into Arabic sources may naturally change this picture.

²¹Sauvaget, Introduction to Akhbār.

²²Iṣṭakhrī, pp. 97-98. Ibn Hawqal II, pp. 284-285 visited Basra in 350 A.H. (961) and met Sirāfīs there.

²³See Chapter 7 below.

²⁴Needham IV(3), p. 496; E. Axleson, South East Africa 1488-1530, Oxford 1962. Needham IV(3), p. 495 notes the finds of porcelain from East Africa and concludes that "these are many indeed, so many that it is rather hard to believe they all came there through intermediate traffickers". By the archaeological standards of the Gulf

finds from East Africa are minute. The largest surface collection from there seems to be a mere 400 sherds from 30 sites. On a single site in the Gulf I have collected 15,000 Chinese sherds, and that was merely a sample. Statistical analysis suggests that the total number on the surface of this site exceeded 500,000. Indeed, the very small number of finds from East Africa is evidence against direct shipment from China.

²⁵ e.g. E. H. L. Schwarz, "Chinese Connections with Africa", J.R.A.S. Bengal, 1938, pp. 175ff.

²⁶ Idrīsī, trans. Jaubert II, pp. 59-60. For Chinese trade with the islands, Idrīsī I, p. 58; p. 65 for trade between Zānej Island and East African mainland (Zanj, without pointing). Idrīsī's account is examined in detail in Chapter 11 below.

²⁷ e.g. F. J. Moorhead, A History of Malaya and her neighbours, London 1957 I, p. 85. The most recent treatment of the subject is H. Deschamps, "Indonesians at the Origins of Madagascar and in Africa (Hypothesis, data, and problems)", Lecture given to the Mombasa Congress 1967. J. Duyvendak, China's Discovery of Africa, London 1949, p. 16, considers that the Chinese did not reach Africa till after the Sung.

²⁸ Information on Islamic shipping is noted in Hourani, pp. 89 ff. and below. Chinese shipping is described in Needham IV(3), pp. 379ff.

²⁹ Warmington, p. 138.

³⁰ Amm. Marc. XIV, 3, 3; Hudson, p. 113; Hourani, p. 48. P. Pelliot, Notes on Marco Polo, Paris 1959, I, pp. 267 f. disputes this distinction and derives Sīn from a Malay word.

³¹ Liu Sung Shu 97, 29.

³² Ta-ts'in, which is often indicated as [Syria], e.g. by Hirth or Needham IV(3), p. 602, seems on other occasions to refer to the whole eastern Mediterranean area "the Roman Orient" and even beyond. Wolters, p. 40 considered that "it represented the Roman Provinces in the Middle East, and also, no doubt, other Middle Eastern countries with which Roman citizens from the eastern Mediterranean trade.

³³ Hirth, p. 46.

³⁴ Wang, p. 54.

³⁵ Wolters, p. 77, quoted. He discusses his translation on p. 285, note 27.

- ³⁶Wang, p. 54.
- ³⁷Needham I, p. 179, note c.
- ³⁸Wolters, pp. 77, 146.
- ³⁹The T'oung Tien of Tou Yeou.
- ⁴⁰P. Pelliot, "Des artisans chinois à la capitale Abbasside en 751-762" T'oung Pao XXVI, 1929, pp. 110-112.
- ⁴¹Tibbetts, p. 2, note 2 on the authority of Gibson Hill [C.A.].
- ⁴²The New History of the T'ang, Chapter 43 G.
- ⁴³Ibn Kh. pp. 42-45.
- ⁴⁴P. Pelliot, "Deux itinéraires de Chine en Inde à la fin du VIII^e siècle," B.E.F.E.O., IV, 1904, pp. 131-413; Wheatley, p. 47.
- ⁴⁵Introduction to CJK, pp. 10-14.
- ⁴⁶T. Lewicki, "Les premiers commerçants Arabes en Chine", Rocznik Orientalistyczny XI, 1935, pp. 173-186.
- ⁴⁷Ibn Kh. pp. 42-43 has the coasting itinerary; pp. 43-45, the monsoon route. For Sulaymān's itinerary see above.
- ⁴⁸It is illustrated in G. Yazdani and L. Binion, Ajanta-The Colour and Monochrome Reproductions of the Ajanta Frescoes Based on Photography, London 1933, part II (Plates), pl. 42.
- ⁴⁹J. Allen in ibid., Text II, p. 57, concluded on paleographical grounds that all eleven inscriptions in Cave II dated from the first half of the 6th century and that the ship painting was contemporary. (See also R. K. Mookerji, Indian Shipping. A History of the Seaborne Trade and Maritime Activity of the Indians from the Earliest Times, 2nd edition, Bombay 1957, p. 28.
- The date of c. 630 adapted by so many scholars (e.g. Hourani, pl. 4, facing p. 35; R. le B. Bowen, "The Origins of Fore-and-Aft Rigs", A.N.E.P.T. 19, 1959, p. 192; even Needham, while noting Mookerji's view, IV(3), p. 454, elsewhere describes the ship as 7th century, p. 606 Table 72) is based on two assumptions. The first is that the court scene illustrated in Cave I represents a Persian embassy to the Hindu Pulakesin Raja of the Deccan in c. 628. This is the view of Hasan, pp. 88-90 and Mookerji, p. 29, but other scholars have seriously doubted whether an envoy to a Hindu ruler would be depicted in a Buddhist cave, and have suggested that it represents a pilgrim scene or an unidentified jataka. See

G. Yazdani and L. Binion, Ajanta-The Colour and Monochrome Reproductions of the Ajanta Frescoes Based on Photography, London I (1930), pp. 46-48. The second assumption depends on the first and is that the ship in Cave II is that which carried the Persian envoys. This case has been strongly argued by the Persian scholar H. Hasan, although he only worked from verbal descriptions of the ship. It has however, been accepted by most scholars who have neglected Yazdani and Bowen's exhaustive study.

⁵⁰W. H. Schoff, The Periplus of the Erythraean Sea, New York 1912, pp. 247-248.

⁵¹I. A. Donnelly, "Early Chinese Ships and Trade", Mariner's Mirror, XI, 1925, pp. 344-354. R. le B. Bowen, "Eastern Sail Affinities", A.N.E.P.T. 13, 1953, p. 194 is incorrect in referring to Hornell's opinion on the Ajanta boat as being in his "Origins and Ethnological Significance of Indian Boat Designs", Memoirs of the Asiatic Society of Bengal VII, 1920, p. 203. This passage refers to Marco Polo's descriptions of boats in India.

⁵²R. K. Mookerji, Indian Shipping. A History of the Seaborne Trade and Maritime Activity of the Indians from the Earliest Times, 2nd edition, Bombay 1957, pp. 28-29.

⁵³Hasan, pp. 88-90, see note 2.

⁵⁴R. le B. Bowen, "The origins of Fore-and-Aft Rigs", A.N.E.P.T. 19, 1959, p. 192; "Eastern Sail Affinities", A.N.E.P.T. 13, 1953, pp. 194-197, quoted p. 194.

⁵⁵Needham IV(3), p. 455.

⁵⁶The Zanzibar hoard is recorded in G. S. P. Freeman-Grenville, The Medieval History of the Coast of Tanganyika, London 1962, p. 184. The Sirāf hoard is discussed in Sirāf III. Chinese coins appear to have remained in circulation in the western Indian Ocean for many centuries and for that reason are virtually useless for dating archaeological levels except in providing a post quem date. A misunderstanding of Chinese coin evidence misled Bibby in dating his 15th c. levels to the 12

⁵⁷See David Whitehouse and Andrew Williamson, "Sasanian Maritime Trade", Iran XI, 1973, pp. 29-49.

⁵⁸The historical background in China and the Chinese demand for western products is discussed in the second half of this Chapter.

⁵⁹See especially Wheatley, pp. 14-25. K'ang Tia's mission is discussed below.

⁶⁰Mentioned in Needham IV(3), p. 449.

⁶¹M.S. Levi, "Les missions de Wang Hiuen-Ts'e dans l'Inde", J.A. 1900, pp. 401-468.

⁶²Fa-Hsien, The Travels of Fa-Hsien, trans. E. A. Giles, Cambridge 1923, p. 68.

⁶³Wolters, p. 146.

⁶⁴Liang Shu 33, quoted in Wolters, p. 146.

⁶⁵Wang, p. 60; Wolters, p. 286, note 41.

⁶⁶Quoted in Needham IV(3), p. 453.

⁶⁷Introduction to CJK, p. 15, note 3.

⁶⁸Needham IV(3), p. 449.

⁶⁹Ya^cqūbī, Ta'rīkh, ed. Houtsma, Leiden 1883, pp. 205-207; Mas^cūdī, Murūj, I, pp. 292-293; G. Ferrand, "Les relations de la Chine avec le Golfe Persique avant l'Hégire", Mélanges Gaudefroy-Demombynes, Cairo 1935-1945, pp. 131-140.

⁷⁰Needham's phrase, I, p. 194.

⁷¹Quoted in Needham IV(3), pp. 487-488.

⁷²Mas^cūdī, Murūj, II, p. 200; A.D.H. Bivar, "Trade Between China and the Near East in the Sasanian and early Muslim Periods", P.M.T.C., p. 2. Malcom's most romantic translation (History of Persia, I, pp. 144-145) which was quoted in Yula: I, p. 95, and more recently by E. H. Schafer, "Iranian Merchants in Thang Dynasty Tales", Semitic and Oriental Studies 11, 1951, p. 403, is unfortunately almost totally incorrect.

⁷³Hirth, p. 35.

⁷⁴Ibid, p. 39; Wolters, p. 42.

⁷⁵Wolters, p. 82; E. H. Schafer, "Iranian Merchants in Thang Dynasty Tales", Semitic and Oriental Studies 11, 1951, p. 403; Laufer, p. 471 dates the embassy to 461.

⁷⁶Wang, pp. 147-148 and note 67 on p. 311.

⁷⁷Needham IV(3), p. 444, noted that a few scholars have identified P'i-tsung, reached by sea by a Han envoy in A.D. 1-5, as Ethiopia. Wheatley, pp. 11-12 and others have no hesitation in placing it in Malaya, since it is mentioned as half way on the route from South India to An-nam.

⁷⁸Hirth, pp. 35-36; Needham I, p. 196.

⁷⁹Wang, p. 126.

⁸⁰Discussed below. See especially Wang, p. 70.

⁸¹Discussed below. See especially Wheatley, pp. 14-25.

⁸²See especially Wheatley, pp. 26-36.

⁸³This fascinating reminiscence is recorded in Needham IV(3), pp. 507-508.